

THE CONNECTION BETWEEN LIFESTYLE EDIAND MCINE

**Health is not everything,
but without health, everything is nothing!**
Socrates

Khusainova Mukhiba Shavkatovna

Samarkand Abu Ali Ibn Sino Public Health Technical University,
teachers of the Department of Community Nursing

Khakimova Kh.Kh.

Senior Lecturer at the Department of Public Health and
Healthcare Management, SamMU

Abstract. This article is devoted to the problems of improving the quality of life and strengthening human health in modern conditions, as well as the influence of physical culture and sports on the formation of a healthy lifestyle (HLS). The importance of physical culture and sports is highlighted as one of the most affordable and effective means that have a beneficial effect on people's health.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена проблемам повышения качества жизни и укрепления здоровья человека в современных условиях, а также влиянию физической культуры и спорта на формирование здорового образа жизни (ЗОЖ). Подчеркивается важность физической культуры и спорта как одного из самых доступных и эффективных средств, благотворно влияющих на здоровье людей.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola zamonaviy sharoitda hayot sifatini oshirish va inson salomatligini mustahkamlash muammolariga, shuningdek, jismoniy madaniyat va sportning sogʻlom turmush tarzini (STT) shakllantirishdagi roliga bagʻishlangan. Jismoniy madaniyat va sportning odamlarning salomatligiga ijobiy taʼsir

koʻrsatadigan eng qulay va samarali vositalardan biri sifatidagi ahamiyati taʼkidlangan.

Keywords: quality of life, health, healthy lifestyle, sport, people.

Ключевые слова: качество жизни, здоровье, здоровый образ жизни, спорт, люди.

Research Objective. The objective of this research is to substantiate the essence of a new concept—quality of health—and the criteria for its classification and evaluation.

Relevance. Improving the quality of life and strengthening human health at the current stage of civilization's development is one of the central tasks of any democratic state.

Materials and Methods. "Quality of life related to health" is a concept used to measure how your health affects your physical, social, and emotional well-being. Health-related quality of life (HRQOL) is a useful indicator of overall health because it captures information about people's physical and mental health, as well as the impact of health on quality of life. Simply put, quality of life is an indicator of a person's well-being and happiness. This concept is broad and characterizes not only material things but also the spiritual aspect of each individual's existence. The definition varies depending on the area of application. A healthy lifestyle is a way of life aimed at preventing diseases and strengthening health. A healthy lifestyle helps us achieve our goals and objectives, successfully implement our plans, cope with difficulties, and, if necessary, withstand tremendous overloads. Strong health, maintained and strengthened by the individual, allows them to live a long and joyful life. Health is an invaluable asset for each individual and society as a whole. When meeting and parting with loved ones, we always wish them good health because it is the main condition for a full and happy life. In any living organism, there is a genetically embedded program—"survive at any cost." That is how the world is structured. Dreaming of longevity, humans have always tried to invent a miracle

remedy that stops aging. Perhaps, in the near future, scientists will indeed be able to significantly increase human life expectancy thanks to revolutionary breakthroughs in science and technology in the 21st century. However, an increase in the number of years will not satisfy anyone without proper quality, so the problem of improving it against this background looks particularly relevant. The term "quality of life" began to be actively used after it was mentioned by U.S. President John F. Kennedy in connection with studies on the standard of living. Initially, this concept was associated only with the health of the population, environmental protection, and urban development. Currently, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), quality of life is defined as a complex of individual perceptions of people's position in life in the context of the culture and value system to which they belong. Health, as defined in the WHO Constitution of 1948, is "a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." Health promotion is "the process of enabling people to increase control over and improve their health" (Ottawa Charter for Health Promotion, 1986, WHO). The Jakarta Declaration, adopted in July 1997, identifies five priority areas for health promotion in the 21st century:

1. Strengthening social responsibility for health.
2. Increasing investments in health development.
3. Consolidating and expanding partnerships for health promotion.
4. Enhancing community and individual capacities and providing real opportunities for action.
5. Securing the infrastructure necessary for health.

In essence, quality of life is the most important aspect of our existence. Whatever a person strives for, it is always directly or indirectly related to various improvements in their life. It is also important to note that this concept is very subjective and ambiguous; everyone understands it in their own way, depending on individual preferences. Therefore, all issues related to the standard of living should be

considered mainly from general positions and patterns. Since the "quality of life" and health are closely interconnected, the main indicators and components of life well-being are:

- Psychological well-being;
- Social well-being;
- Physical well-being;
- Spiritual well-being.

The presence of all four components in people's lives indicates a high standard of living. However, achieving good results is not enough; one must also be able to maintain them. A person is constantly exposed to a large number of negative factors. Threats can come from the state of the environment, unhealthy diet, lack of medical care, totalitarian regimes, financial instability, and much more. Heredity also plays a significant role, as the state of the body and human behavior are largely genetically programmed. As much as we might wish otherwise, the lives of newborns do not start from equal positions. Despite this, the will to live and perseverance sometimes work miracles. As one sage said, "The most valuable thing a person has is life, and the most valuable thing in life is health, which must be fought for with all one's strength." According to many experts and WHO data, people's health depends on lifestyle by at least 50%, on heredity by 20%, on environmental influences by 20%, and on healthcare factors by 10%. Improving the quality of life is a strategic task for societal development. Humanity should strive to ensure that each subsequent generation lives in more comfortable conditions than the previous one. Our well-being directly depends on the correct social policies of the state. A state that does not see its main value in a healthy individual and population as a whole will ultimately lose its primary capital—human resources. Many resources are involved in preserving health.

The most important condition for strengthening health and finding harmony is a healthy lifestyle (HLS). It is based primarily on physical activity, physical

education, and sports. Sports in a person's life, according to both general and personal opinion, is a powerful and effective factor in preserving health. It contributes to the harmonious development of a person. Engaging in physical culture and sports is the main driving force that supports and ensures the normal functioning of all organs and systems in the human body and affects the duration and quality of life. Physical education and sports provide a boost of energy and optimism, strengthen the immune system, and protect a person from various diseases. Sports also bring excellent mood, high vitality, and extraordinary spiritual uplift, forming a solid foundation for striving for success, new achievements, and productive work. It is important that each of us understands this, feels it, and puts it into practice.

Conclusion. Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Health is the normal psychosomatic state of a person, reflecting their complete physical, mental, and social well-being and ensuring the full performance of labor, social, and biological functions.
- Health largely depends on lifestyle. However, when talking about a healthy lifestyle, the absence of bad habits is primarily considered. This is, of course, a necessary but not sufficient condition. The main thing in a healthy lifestyle is the active creation of health, including all its components. Thus, the concept of a healthy lifestyle is much broader than the absence of bad habits, work and rest schedules, nutrition systems, various hardening and developmental exercises; it also includes a system of attitudes towards oneself, others, life in general, as well as the meaningfulness of existence, life goals, and values, etc. Therefore, creating health requires both expanding ideas about health and disease and skillfully using the entire spectrum of factors influencing various components of health (physical, mental, social, and spiritual), mastering health-improving, strengthening, and nature-based

methods and technologies, and forming an attitude towards a healthy lifestyle.

- A healthy lifestyle largely depends on a person's value orientation, worldview, and social and moral experience. Social norms and values of a healthy lifestyle are accepted by students as personally significant, but they do not always coincide with the values developed by public consciousness.

References:

1. Shomurotovna R. Y. Comprehensive analysis of the problem of professional maladaptation quality and health status of nursing //zamonaviy ta'lim: muammo va yechimlari. – 2022. – Т. 1. – С. 47-48.
2. Хакимовна Х. Х. О 'quvchilar jismoniy tarbiyasi tizimida qattish //barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali. – 2022. – С. 378-381.
3. Хакимовна ХХ и др. РЕФОРМЫ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОГО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Европейский журнал молекулярной и клинической медицины. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 2. – С. 820-827. Хакимовна ХХ и др. РЕФОРМЫ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОГО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Европейский журнал молекулярной и клинической медицины. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 2. – С. 820-827.
4. Xonbuvi H. Yunusov Sardor Ashrafzoda indicator functions in medicine galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal (giirj) issn (e): 2347-6915 Vol. 12. – 2024.
5. Naimova Z. et al. Influence Of Ecotoxicants From A Chemical Plant On The Dynamics Of Child Morbidity //The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research. – 2021. – С. 56-59. Naimova Z. et al. Influence Of Ecotoxicants From A Chemical Plant On The Dynamics Of

- Child Morbidity //The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research. – 2021. – С. 56-59.
6. Khakimova H. H., Barotova R. S. THE IMPORTANCE OF PREVENTION IN MEDICAL PRACTICE //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 96-98.
7. Наимова З. и др. Гигиеническая оценка влияния выбросов химического предприятия на условия жизни, благополучие и здоровье населения // Американский журнал медицинских наук и фармацевтических исследований. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 01. – С. 76-80.
8. Хакимова Х. Х., Баротова Р. С. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ В МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ //Сеть медицины: Журнал медицины, практики и сестринского дела. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 96-98.
9. Хакимова Х., Худойназарова Н. Е. СПОРЫ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ МЕДИЦИНСКОГО РАБОТНИКА //Сеть медицины: Журнал медицины, практики и сестринского дела. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 66-70.
10. Тухтаров Б. и др. Эколого-гигиеническая оценка загрязнения почв тяжелыми металлами и разработка мероприятий по его улучшению //Каталог монографий. – 2023. – №. 1. – С. 2-110.